

Extraction and isolation of lignin derivatives from roots of *Argemone mexicana* L.

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Abstract : Extraction, isolation and characterization of five lignins from roots of *Argemone mexicana* have been described in this communication.

Keywords : Lignin derivatives, *Argemone mexicana*.

This communication describes extraction, isolation and characterisation of total lignin and lignin derivatives from the whole plant of *Argemone mexicana* L. (Family : Papaveraceae). Lignin content 1 was obtained by treating the sample of *Argemona mexicana* with sulphuric acid and then this reaction mixture was diluted with distilled water and refluxed to obtain 1. Organosolv lignin 2 was obtained by digesting meal sample in autoclave with aqueous alcohol-hydrochloric acid. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate during distillation yielded the crystals of 2.

Chlorinated lignin 3 was obtained as when moist meal sample was chlorinated and subsequently washed with hot ethanol. The alcoholic filtrate was collected. This process was repeated until meal sample got white. The filtrate was concentrated and poured into excess of ice cold water when white crystals of 3 were separated out. Sulphonated lignin 4 was extracted by digesting the meal sample with aqueous sodium sulphite and sodium bisulphite in autoclave. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was distilled to concentrate the filtrate. It was placed in ice bath and concentrated H₂SO₄ was added

Lignin monomer units :

Compd.	Name of compd.	(S)-R = Syringyl derivative	(H)-R = <i>p</i> -Hydrophenyl derivative	(G)-R = Guaiacyl derivative	Monomer, obtained in macromolecules confirmed by spectroscopical analysis
		(S)-R	(H)-R	(G)-R	
1	Lignin content	Yes	Yes	No	(S)-R (NMR and IR) (H)-R (NMR)
2	Organosolv lignin	Yes	No	Yes	(S)-R (NMR) (G)-R (NMR and IR)
3	Chlorinated lignin	No	Yes	Yes	(H)-R (NMR and IR) (G)-R (NMR)
4	Sulphonated lignin	Yes	No	No	(S)-R (NMR and IR)
5	Alkali lignin	No	No	Yes	(G)-R (NMR and IR)

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 1 to 5

Compd.	Colour of compd.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1	Dark brown crystalline	300	28.30
2	Light grey crystalline	311	30.38
3	White crystalline	291	32.40
4	Light brown crystalline	275	31.33
5	Dark brown crystalline	210	41.90

dropwise to obtain light brown crystals of 4. Alkali lignin 5 was extracted by digesting meal sample with aqueous NaOH in autoclave. The content was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was acidified in cold condition with dilute HCl to obtain 5.

The spectral analysis of each lignin showed hydroxyl (H)-R, guaiacyl (G)-R and syringyl units (S)-R in lignin macromolecule.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and uncorrected. IR spectra (Nujol) were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra on Bruker DRX300 spectrometer. Whole plants of *Argemone mexicana* were collected in Morshi Tahsil in January 2003, shed dried and pulverised in grinding mill. This sample was used for the extraction of lignin content and its derivatives.

Extraction and isolation of 1 :

Grinded oven dried sample powder of *Argemone mexicana* L. (6 g) was treated with H₂SO₄ (72%, 90 ml) at 20° for 1 h with stirring. Then it was diluted with distilled water (60 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h in round bottom flask to obtain dark brown crystals of 1 (3.1 g).

Extraction and isolation of 2 to 5 were carried out by giving previous treatment to the sample of Argemone mexicana as depicted below :

Sample of *Argemone mexicana* (15 g) was packed in an extraction thimble and extracted in a soxhlet extractor with hot ethanol : benzene (1 : 2) for 6 h. The sample was then again extracted with ethanol for 6 h. It was then taken out and dried to give meal sample of *Argemone mexicana* which is extractive free.

Extraction and isolation of 2 : Meal sample (24 g) was digested with aqueous alcohol (50%, 240 ml), in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid (2.4 ml) in autoclave for 4 h at 90 psi. The mixture was filtered and filtrate

was distilled to obtain 2 (9.4 g). The crystallisation was carried out in dioxane-water mixture.

Extraction and isolation of 3 : Meal sample was moistened with distilled water. Chlorination of meal sample (6 g) was carried out by passing chlorine gas into. It was then washed with hot ethanol, this process was repeated continuously until meal sample change its colour to white, the alcoholic filtrate was collected, it was concentrated and poured into excess of ice cold water, white crystals of 3 (3.1 g) were separated out.

Extraction and isolation of 4 :

Meal sample (25.52 g) was digested with sodium sulphite (5.1 g) and sodium metabisulphite (12.7 g) in presence of distilled water (135 ml) in autoclave for 3 h at 120 psi. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was distilled to remove the excess of water. The concentrated filtrate was kept in ice bath and concentrated H₂SO₄ was added dropwise maintaining the temperature 0 °C the reaction mixture became acidic. It was kept in ice bath 2 h and then at room condition for overnight to obtain light brown crystal of 4 (9.7 g).

Extraction and isolation of 5 :

Meal sample (16 g) was digested with sodium hydroxide (4.5 g) in distilled water (300 ml) for 4 h at 120 psi. The content was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was acidified in cold condition with dilute HCl to obtain 5 (5.8 g).

Compound 1 :

Dark brown crystalline solid; m.p. 318 °C ; soluble in MeOH, DMSO, CHCl₃ and TFA; ν_{\max} 3278 (OH), 2925 (OH-stretching in CH₃ and CH₂ group), 2858 (OH-stretching in CH₂ group), 2727 (C-H), 1535 (aromatic skeletal vibration), 1458 (C-H deformation asymmetric), 1377 (syringyl ring breathing with CO stretching), 1163 and 1238 (aromatic C-H plane deformation)¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.96 (3H, s), 2.25 (2H, t), 2.54 (1H, s), 3.5 (1H, m), 4.4 (1H, d), 5.07 (1H, d), 7.32 (Ar-H)³.

Compound 2 :

Light grey crystalline solid; m.p. 310 °C; soluble in MeOH, CDCl₃ and TFA; ν_{\max} 3400 (O-H hydrogen bond), 2925 (O-H stretching in CH₃ and CH₂ groups), 2858 (O-H stretching in CH₂ group), 2700 (C-H stretch), 1743 (C=O), 1627 (C=C), 1458 (CH₂ bending), 1375 (CH₃ bending), 1025–1271 (aromatic C-H in-plane deformation guaiacyl type and C-O deformation primary alcohol), 727 (aromatic C-H out-of-plane bending); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.92 (3H, s), 1.37 (3H, s), 2.17

(1H, t), 4.25 (2H, bt), 5.7 (Ar-OH, s), 7.2 (Ar-H, bs), 8.04 (Ar-2H, bs)¹.

Compound 3 :

White crystals; m.p. 290 °C; soluble in MeOH, CDCl₃ and TFA; ν_{\max} 3284 (OH), 9085 (Ar-H), 1635 (C-stretching *p*-substituted alkyl ketone), 1447 (C-H deformation asymmetric), 925–1230 (Ar-bending), 1072 (C-O deformation sec. alcohol and aliphatic ether); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.25 (3H, s) 1.96 (2H, s), 3.4–3.8 (1H, bm)².

Compound 4 :

Light brown crystals; m.p. 284 °C; soluble in MeOH, CDCl₃ and DMSO; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.56 (2H, s), 2.45 (2H, s), 2.9 (3H, t), 3.8 (3H, bs), 7.36 (Ar-H).

Compound 5 :

Dark brown crystals; m.p. 257 °C; soluble in MeOH, CHCl₃ and DMSO; ν_{\max} 3406 (O-H), 3193 (Ar-H), 2923 (OH stretch in Me and CH₂ group), 2840 (OH stretch in CH₂), 1720 (C=O), 1026 (C-O), 957–1305 (aromatic C-

H in-plane deformation), 852 (*p*-disubstituted ring); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.27 (3H, s), 2.76 (3H, s), 2.82 (1H, m), 7.45 (4H, dd)^{2,3}.

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